

Groundnut Roasting Machine using Induction Heating

Hariharan M^{1*}, Hariharan B², Rojar Gimson A³, Joshuva Vasanthan K⁴, Raj Kumar k⁵

^{1,2,3,4}Student, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Saranathan College of Engineering, India.

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Saranathan College of Engineering, India.

*Corresponding Author

DoI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15333928>

Abstract

Traditional groundnut roasting methods that use firewood and gas contribute significantly to deforestation, carbon emissions, and health risks for street vendors. To address these issues, this project proposes a solar-powered induction heating groundnut roaster that is energy-efficient and environmentally friendly. The system incorporates a Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) converter for improved efficiency and reduced switching losses [1][2][7]. An Arduino microcontroller automates temperature monitoring and control, enabling precise roasting and minimizing human intervention [3][11]. A motor-driven stirrer ensures uniform heat distribution, enhancing the overall roasting quality [5][6]. The system is powered by a solar photovoltaic panel with a battery backup to ensure uninterrupted operation even during low sunlight periods [4][12]. This innovative solution supports clean energy use, reduces operational costs, and improves the livelihood of street vendors by providing a safer and more reliable roasting method.

Keywords: Solar-Powered Roasting, Induction Heating, Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS), LC Tank Circuit, Temperature Control, Microcontroller-Based System, Real-Time Monitoring, Energy-Efficient.
